

MODERN REQUIREMENTS FOR LEADERSHIP RESEARCH COMPETENCIES

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Abstract: This article discusses the theoretical foundations of the modern requirements for managerial research competences in the educational system.

Key words: Educational system, scientific research activity, theory, methodology.

Nowadays, it is no coincidence that the level of scientific and research competencies of any specialist, especially the leading personnel in the educational system, directly affects the quality and efficiency of management. Because a modern specialist, in addition to having general methodological and methodological knowledge of his field, should be able to effectively use innovative methods in his work, analyze the problem, work with a large amount of information, draw reasonable and correct conclusions. such skills should be continuously and systematically developed. A person's level of knowledge is determined by his ability to solve problems in practice. Competence is a combination of interrelated qualities of a person and is a factor that determines the ability to perform effective and productive activities.

A pedagogue, like any specialist, should be able to develop an "Individual development program" of a personal and practical nature, based on which pedagogical

it is necessary to start the activity.

Individual development program (IRD) - a personal-practical program developed on the basis of the needs of each person or specialist to form and develop certain qualities, VKM, professional competence, self-development, professional experience, qualifications and should independently organize

practical actions based on clear goals and well-thought-out tasks to improve skills. The qualities of professional competence are as follows:

1. Social competence.

1) possession of skills and qualifications to interact with social organizations and subjects;

2) ability to master professional communication and behavior styles;

2. Personal competence.

1) to constantly achieve professional growth and improve professional qualifications;

2) being able to realize one's own potential in professional activity;

3. Special competence.

1) preparing to organize professional-pedagogical activities independently;

2) having the ability to correctly solve the usual professional and pedagogical tasks and realistically evaluate the results of one's work;

3) having the ability to independently and consistently acquire new knowledge and skills in the specialty;

4. Technological competence.

1) ability to master advanced technologies that enrich professional-pedagogical knowledge, skills and qualifications;

2) the ability to use modern didactic tools (technical tools, educational tools);

5. Extreme competence.

1) in emergency situations (in case of natural disasters, technological process failure), ability to make rational decisions and act correctly;

2) in problematic situations (when pedagogical conflicts arise), it is to have the skills to make a rational decision, to act correctly.

Thus, in the conditions of market relations, every specialist has the need to withstand strong competition in the labor market

encourages the formation of professional competence and qualities specific to it.

In terms of vocabulary, it is "ability", and in terms of content, it is "the effective use of theoretical knowledge in the activity, it shows a high level of professional competence, skill and talent

On the basis of competence, which means "to get", certain qualities are not good will be.

Below is the scientific research that we will need to train the education manager

We present a model of competencies. For this, it is appropriate to determine the general and professional competencies of the future leader. General competences (basic, decisive, universal) include knowledge gained during the

entire educational process and in practice, experience, and the ability to know methods and terms acquired in certain fields. General competencies necessary for professional and scientific activities can be divided into 3 types: instrumental, interpersonal and personal.

Instrumental competence means the ability to understand and apply cognitive thoughts and ideas, and methodological skills, that is, organizing work time, making decisions, choosing a study strategy, etc., technological skills (use of various technical tools and computers ability to use) and certain linguistic skills are understood.

One of the basic instrumental competences is information competence. Its content includes mastering various technical devices, computer technologies, obtaining the necessary information from various sources, being able to use them effectively in a generalized way, analytical processing of information, knowing the characteristics of the flow of information in one's field, and a number of other skills. includes. As can be seen from the content of information competence, it is necessary to form them in solving various everyday and professional problems, but there are several features that indicate that this competence is fundamental.

Information competence is multi-faceted, requires re-mental development for the formation of special abilities, qualities such as abstract thinking, determination of one's point of view are required.

Instrumental competence is divided into the following groups: competences in acquiring knowledge; Competencies of creating a hypothesis, predicting results; competences to choose ways to optimally solve problems and to implement them; critical evaluation and explanation competences of obtained results.

Interpersonal competencies are social skills and their implementation reflects the application of abilities in research activities. Interpersonal the level of competence formation reflects the researcher's ability to work with a team, the realization of interpersonal relationships. A person's communicative competence (communicative awareness) indicates the effectiveness of his participation in the process of socio-cultural communication, the existence of active and sufficient conditions for the implementation and actualization of various functions by the subject in society.

The following can be included in the interpersonal competencies of a leader in research activities:

- ability to work in different groups;
- feeling responsibility for the task performed in the group;

- striving to regulate mutual relations in the group without conflicts;
- feel satisfaction from professional communication;
- to demonstrate the ability to regulate interaction between individuals as a project leader, to have a positive influence on subordinates;

The personal competencies of a leader in research activity are as follows:

- independent in various spheres of activity, including scientific and professional spheres

show thinking;

- to take the initiative in the process of working with the group and to support the initiatives of others;

- have creative thinking, always strive for innovation;

- have critical thinking;

- to have a high level of moral reflection;

- self-control, self-analysis, self-assessment;

- development of volitional qualities, emotional in case of failure

be able to manage the situation.

Therefore, instrumental competence reflects the realization of the ability to understand and apply cognitive thoughts and ideas, the ability of the researcher to work with a team at the level of the formation of interpersonal competencies, the ability to establish interpersonal relationships correctly, The personal competencies of a leader in scientific and research activities are creativity, critical thinking, moral reflection, self-control, analysis, and the ability to develop willpower.

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